

SYSTEM OF LAND STRUCTURE DESIGN IN UZBEKISTAN AND ITS
MAIN CONTENT

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Abstract:

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About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

At the present time, a precise land formation system has been established in Uzbekistan, which is included in the field of land resources management of our country and includes the implementation of land laws, organization of effective and full use of land, land protection, creation of a clean ecological environment and natural landscapes. performs tasks such as improvement.

Yer tuzish tizimi quyidagi tarkibiy qismlardan iborat:

- ❖ Land preparation works prescribed by laws;
- ❖ clear, legally defined order of land construction works;
- ❖ approved list of land acquisition documents;
- ❖ specially organized land preparation service engaged in land preparation activities;
- ❖ organization of land preparation;
- ❖ land preparation participants;
- ❖ system of training, retraining and upgrading of specialists

The main part of earthworks is carried out with the help of earthworks projects. That's why the land structure design system is of great importance. This system includes the stages of pre-project, design and project implementation.

At the pre-project stage, the following documents are processed for the purposes of land structure design::

- ❖ administrative district land layout drawings;
- ❖ drawings of some land construction works related to development and placement of production forces, development of agro-industry production and its branches, improvement of land relations, land ownership and land use, design of nature protection measures;

❖ Feasibility calculations of the implementation of land management activities related to land use and protection in the territories of a group of land owners and land users, project objects.

The district land development plan is the main pre-project document and determines the most effective ways of using and protecting the district's land resources in the future (not less than 10-15 years). It shows the main ways of developing the agro-industrial complex and other branches of the district, the system of land ownership and land users.

The following issues will be resolved in the district zoning plan:

❖ justifying their requirements for land resources, taking into account the development of district economic sectors in the future;

❖ determination of lands suitable for use in agriculture and other sectors and determining the order of their development;

❖ distribution of land among sectors, improvement of the system of land ownership and land use and elimination of deficiencies in their land;

❖ determining the ways of intensive use of land resources and increasing the productivity of agricultural land;

to determine the future development and territorial location of economic centers, production and social infrastructure networks;

❖ preparation of proposals for increasing the production of agricultural products;

❖ development of land and nature protection measures;

❖ determining the amount of capital funds, material and labor resources necessary for the implementation of the specified activities and evaluating their economic efficiency.

Based on some of the issues facing the land zoning system, in the implementation of land laws, land reform, and independent implementation of nature protection measures, some drawings aimed at land use and protection may be developed as part of the district land zoning plan.

Such drawings may include:

❖ map of land redistribution in the district territory;

❖ plan of anti-erosion measures;

❖ diagram of reclamation of disturbed lands;

❖ map of internal roads in the district;

❖ diagram of placement, specialization and expansion of agricultural production.

These drawings are also part of the pre-project documents and are used in the development of land development projects.

Feasibility studies and calculations are also used as pre-project work. Such justifications and calculations are mainly used in the implementation of irrigation and reclamation works, as well as in the construction of related hydrotechnical structures and in the design of other complex objects. Their main task is to justify the necessity and economic efficiency of the above-mentioned works, to find the most effective ways and methods of carrying out these works, and to determine the order of their implementation.

Regional programs for the use of land resources and their protection can also be used as a pre-project basis for land use planning. They include the deadlines for the implementation of complex activities on the organization of land use and land protection, executors, necessary material, labor and other resources.

The problems to be solved are divided into the following types depending on their content: new land development program; soil erosion protection program; degraded land restoration program; soil fertility improvement program and others.

The basis for the work of regional programs is the results of similar programs developed at the national level, as well as the results of land use and land protection forecasting.

In order to make informed decisions on the effective use of land and water resources and the organization of land protection at the republic level, the land surveying service develops a master plan for the use of land and water resources and land protection of our country (regions). On the basis of these drawings, regional zoning drawings are developed. District zoning maps are processed with greater accuracy than regional zoning maps. They receive solutions on the main issues of land development. These solutions later serve as a basis for inter-farm, intra-farm land development, land reclamation, residential areas, road construction and other engineering projects.

If necessary, searches and researches are carried out before the construction of the land development project. These works include topography-geodesy, soil, soil erosion, soil reclamation, geobotany, water management, roads, study of population living system and exploration and study related to land formation. The results of research and studies and land cadastral documents serve as the basis for project work. These works are also carried out by land preparation service.

On the basis of district land development plans and other pre-project documents, inter-farm and intra-farm land development projects are developed.

Inter-farm land creation projects solve the issues of establishing new agricultural enterprises, closing the gaps in the land of existing enterprises, and allocating land to non-agricultural enterprises.

Only on the basis of the project of inter-farm land construction, documents granting land ownership and land use rights are issued to enterprises,

organizations, institutions and citizens. Land owners and land users can start their activities only after the inter-farm land construction project is transferred to the land and the boundaries of the farms are clearly marked with boundary markers.

Domestic land development projects on farms are drawn up only for agricultural enterprises. Their main task is to rationally and efficiently organize land use and land protection, as well as means of production inseparably connected with land. That is why internal land development projects on farms include not only the organization of agricultural enterprise territories, but also the issues of the organization of the population's living system, production, labor, and management..

The following main issues are resolved in the project of internal land formation in farms:

- ❖ distribution of land among economic departments, placement of economic and production centers, placement of main highways and other engineering objects of general economic importance;
- ❖ determination of economic and ecologically based composition of land types of the farm, transfer and improvement of land from one type to another type;
- ❖ development of a system of placement of trees, rotation of crops, rotation of pastures and hayfields, organization of their territories;
- ❖ establishing mandatory requirements and standards for land use for land owners and land users.

For the purpose of step-by-step implementation of the land development measures envisaged in the land development projects, in some cases, working projects on land use and land protection are drawn up for specific land plots in the district land development plans.

These projects include all activities that require capital funds for the use of land and other land-related means of production and land protection. These activities include development of new land, improvement of the quality of agricultural land, land reclamation, construction of irrigation, land reclamation and road networks, creation of parks, tree belts and other tree groves, construction of hydrotechnical structures against erosion and etc. enters.

Working projects serve as a basis for starting financing and implementing specified activities. At the stage of implementation of land development projects, authorship control over the project implementation process is established. If necessary, corrections can be made to the project during authorship control. Authorship control is carried out by land surveying service. It is held in order to ensure timely and correct implementation of project solutions, full compliance with the specified technologies and estimated cost of works, mandatory requirements and standards for land use and land protection.

The results of authorship control are analyzed, the causes of the shortcomings are determined, and measures are developed to eliminate them.

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